

Data-Driven Electrical Machines Structural Model Using the Vibration Synthesis Method

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Abstract— This article proposes a data-driven structural modeling approach for electrical machine airborne vibration that can be used both in the design stage for fast optimization routines and in system-level simulations. This method is able to capture both in-plane and out-of-plane modal behavior along with local effects, such as tooth bending. The model relies on fitting unitary force-shape responses to transfer function models using a zero-pole representation. These frequency response functions are obtained from applying the vibration synthesis process to a series of finite-element (FE) stator models that have material properties updated using the experimental modal analysis. The obtained zeros and poles are used to construct three lookup table models with their accuracy varying between the three of them with the number of samples used in the data generation process. The accuracy of these models is validated at the unitary force-shape response level using four stator FE model samples. Also, at the run-up vibration spectrogram level, the models are validated, with good results, using radial and tangential force excitation obtained from an updated electromagnetic FE model of an interior permanent magnet (PM) synchronous machine designed for electric power steering. The computational cost compared to the standard FE vibration synthesis method is shown.

Index Terms— Data-driven engineering, electrical machine structural model, internal permanent magnet synchronous machine (IPMSM), noise, vibration, and harshness (NVH), vibration synthesis.

I. INTRODUCTION

WITH the electrification of the transportation system and to ensure customer comfort, electrical machine noise, vibration, and harshness (NVH) attributes become an

important target in the electrical machine development process. Traditionally, this process follows a waterfall sequence where the NVH calculations are conducted after the electromagnetic and thermal calculations. Also, usually, the 3-D finite-element (FE) NVH analysis requires more computation effort than the 2-D electromagnetic finite-element analysis (FEA) (for axis-symmetrical machines), thus contributing significantly to the multiphysics computation time. Recently, system-level simulations are also employed early in the design process to check the influence of the control and power electronics on the machine's multiphysical attributes in a dynamic simulation environment [1].

There are several ways to compute the electrical machine vibration response from the air-gap force excitation obtained from the electromagnetic FEA. The simplest and fastest method is to use an analytical representation of the stator via a ring model [2] or a semianalytical model where the stator modal frequencies are obtained from structural FE simulations [3]. The drawback of these methods is that they can only capture the in-plane (i.e., the plane of the machine cross section) modal behavior. Methods that can capture both in-plane and out-of-plane modal behavior, together with local effects such as tooth bending, are computationally expensive but have higher accuracy. In this category, one of the most common methods used is the nodal force mapping approach [4], where the electromagnetic forces computed on the stator (and rotor) electromagnetic FE mesh nodes are applied to the 3-D structural mesh using a projection method. This method is highly accurate but is also computationally expensive and is not suited for system-level simulation. A different magnetomechanical coupling method is the lumped-tooth force approach [1], where the air-gap force density computed via the Maxwell stress tensor (MST) is integrated over the tooth pitches and applied to a state-space matrix that contains mass, damping, and stiffness information obtained from the stator structural modal analysis. This method is well suited for system-level simulation, but attention has to be paid to the tooth pitch discretizations where the lumped-tooth force is calculated in order to preserve the spectral force accuracy [5]. A different approach is that of the vibration synthesis [6] where the vibration response is computed as a superposition of frequency response functions (FRFs) that are excited by the Fourier-decomposed air-gap forces computed with the MST. This method is also suited for machines that have nonsymmetrical forces along the shaft length (skewed and axial flux machines) [7] and can be used in the system-

level simulation [8]. Methods that rely on measured FRFs also exist [9], but they are more difficult to implement because of complicated test requirements.

Data-driven models can be used in the design process where the extensive computational load is done before the target design has to be calculated by computing a series of possible designs, extracting the important data features, and building a fast model from these data. This method is well suited for mass-manufactured machines where a new product version does not change significantly with respect to an older one [10] such that a limited number of degrees of freedom (DOF) have to be explored in the data generation process. Data-driven electromagnetic models that include torque and flux linkages exist [11], [12], but a few studies exist for the structural behavior. A surrogate model [13] based on the semianalytical approach is proposed [3], but this can only capture global modal behavior. The only data-driven structural dynamics model, known to the authors, that can capture both global and local mode shapes uses the vibration impulse responses of the switched reluctance machine (SRM) that are fit to a lookup table (LUT) model using the rational fraction polynomial (RFP) method [14].

In this article, a data-driven model for electrical machine stator vibration response computation is proposed that is well suited for both machine NVH fast computation and system-level simulation, where Fig. 1 shows the workflow. First, the vibration synthesis method (explained in Section III) is applied to several machine stator models using a parameterized model (explained in Section IV-A) that has material properties updated using modal test results from a stator specimen. Afterward, the resulting FRFs are fit to transfer functions in the s -domain using a zeros and poles representation (shown in Section IV-B). Three distinctive LUT models are constructed, and finally, the process is validated (Section V), where air-gap forces obtained from an electromagnetic FE test-updated model are applied to the data-driven models and the run-up vibrations orders are compared. Finally, the computational cost (Section V-D) of constructing the data-driven models is compared to FEA

Fig. 1. Stator data-driven structural modeling using the vibration synthesis method workflow.

are placed at the different axial lengths across the stator circumference. The roving accelerometer method is thus used to measure $H_{o/i}$ by conducting different test sets, where the excitation point is kept fixed, and a limited number of sensors are rotated to cover all the 24 locations. A Simcenter SCADAS Mobile is used for data acquisition and the PolyMAX algorithm from Simcenter Test.Lab [15] is used to estimate the modal parameters: modal damping ζ_k , residues A_k , and natural frequencies ω_k for each mode k , until the maximum truncated mode n in the desired frequency range based on an RFP representation [16] of the linear modal model

$$H_{o/i}(\omega) = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{A_k}{j\omega - \lambda_k} + \frac{A_k^*}{j\omega - \lambda_k^*}$$

with

$$\lambda_k = -\zeta_k \omega_k + j \sqrt{1 - \zeta_k^2} \omega_k \quad (1)$$

where $*$ is the complex conjugate. The driving point FRF measurement where the force input from the impact hammer and the response output from the accelerometer, measured at the same point (in this case, as close as possible) on the stator structure in the radial direction, is shown in Fig. 3.

B. FE Model Updating Based on Anisotropic Material Parameters

After the EMA is performed and the modal parameters are extracted, the CAD-based FE model has to be updated to match the test results. The first step in the model updating procedure is to import the EMA real normal modes in the structural dynamics FE simulation environment. Afterward, the test-based geometry has to be correlated with the FE mesh, and a set of nodes that closely match the EMA sensor positions is chosen [shown in Fig. 2(b)].

II. LAMINATED CORE TEST-BASED MODEL UPDATING

A. Modal Testing Procedure

Experimental modal analysis (EMA) is performed on a stator laminated core sample, as shown in Fig. 2(a). The test aims at estimating output/input FRFs— $H_{o/i}$ in free-free boundary conditions, by suspending the stator sample with an elastic cord. An impact hammer from PCB Piezotronics (model 086B03) is used to impulse-excite the structure. The 24 1-D modal accelerometers from PCB Piezotronics (model 333B32), distributed along the stator outer surface (such that spatial aliasing is avoided), are used to measure the radial vibration response, with the sensor's position on the stator wire-frame mesh shown in Fig. 2(b). Because of the small size of the stator sample, there is no possibility to place all the 24 sensors at once on the stator outer surface. To capture out-of-plane mode shapes with 1-D sensors, a set of sensors

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. (a) EMA test setup where the force excitation hammer is marked with yellow (1) and the 1-D unidirectional (radial) vibration sensors are marked with red (2a–2e) and (b) 24 sensor position on the wire-frame mesh.

Two correlation metrics are used in the optimization routine: the modal frequency difference and the modal assurance criterion (MAC) that is used to determine the similarity of two mode shapes

$$\text{MAC} \{ \psi_i \}_{\text{test}} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\psi_j^{\text{test}} \psi_j^{\text{FE}}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \psi_i^{\text{test}} \psi_i^{\text{FE}}}}{\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\psi_j^{\text{test}} \psi_j^{\text{FE}}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \psi_i^{\text{test}} \psi_i^{\text{FE}}}} \quad (2)$$

where $\{ \psi_i \}_{\text{test}}$ is the i th experimental mode shape and $\{ \psi_i \}_{\text{FE}}$ is the j th simulated one. An MAC value of 1 gives a perfect correlation between the two mode shapes, while ideally, the off-diagonal terms should be zero due to the orthogonality of the modal vectors.

Because the stator core is constructed using a mass production-focused modular technique with a separated tooth segment and back-iron segment that uses axial interlocking on the steel sheets [17], the mechanical material properties

Fig. 3. Stator sample driving point FRF measurement.

is computationally impractical. Even though the stator is in practice a heterogeneous material, the pragmatic approach is to model it as a homogeneous material with the parameters obtained from EMA. The elastic behavior of a node on a mesh can be described by Hooke's law: $\vec{\varepsilon} = S \cdot \vec{\sigma}$, where $\vec{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor that describes the node internal forces (the stress state), $\vec{\varepsilon}$ is the strain tensor that describes the deformation at the node, and S is the compliance matrix [18]. By exploiting the stator symmetries in the cylindrical coordinates system (r, θ, z) , orthotropic behavior can be assumed, thus leading to a total of nine design variables that form the compliance matrix to be explored by the optimization algorithm

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_r} & -\nu_{r\theta} & -\nu_{rz} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{\theta r} & \frac{1}{E_\theta} & -\nu_{\theta z} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{zr} & -\nu_{z\theta} & \frac{1}{E_z} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2G_{rz}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2G_{r\theta}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2G_{\theta z}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{rr} \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{rz} \\ \sigma_{r\theta} \\ \sigma_{z\theta} \end{bmatrix}$$

cannot be considered isotropic. Also, modeling each lamination together with its connection in the FE environment

(3)

where E is Young's modulus, G is the shear module, and ν is the Poisson ratio [19].

The hybrid adaptive algorithm SHERPA from Simcenter HEEDS [20] is chosen to perform the design-space exploration. The MAC number is used to identify and match the FE mode shape to the one obtained from EMA. A 5% constraint, considered sufficient for the model update process, is applied to the mode-shape resonance frequency for the first three mode shapes until 5000 Hz (the bandwidth limit of the testing

Fig. 4. Machine operational deflection shapes obtained from EMA, where the 24 sensor positions are shown on the nondeformed geometry wire-frame (gray) in cylindrical coordinates and correlated FE modal results. (a) Mode shape (2, 0). (b) Mode shape (3, 0). (c) Mode shape (2, 0). (d) Mode shape (3, 0).

TABLE I

NATURAL FREQUENCIES: CALCULATED WITH UPDATED MATERIAL PARAMETERS COMPARED TO EMA

	Measured [Hz]	Updated [Hz]	error [%]
$f_{(2,0)}^1$	1614	1586	-1.7
$f_{(2,0)}^2$	1630	1587	-2.6
$f_{(2,1)}^1$	1642	1720	4.9
$f_{(2,1)}^2$	1653	1721	4.1
$f_{(3,0)}^1$	3868	3869	0.03
$f_{(3,0)}^2$	3907	4067	4.0

system)

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \left| \begin{array}{l} f^{1,2} \\ \text{FE}(2,0) \end{array} - f \right| < 5\% \\
 \left| \begin{array}{l} f^{1,2} \\ \text{FE}(2,1) \end{array} - f_{\text{test}(2,0)}^{1,2} \right| \leq 5\% \\
 \left| \begin{array}{l} f^{1,2} \\ \text{FE}(3,0) \end{array} - f_{\text{test}(3,0)}^{1,2} \right| \leq 5\%
 \end{array} \quad (4)$$

Superscript 1, 2 represents the differentiation between the phase-shifted mode shapes belonging to the same symmetric ($n, 0$) or antisymmetric ($n, 1$) mode class, caused by an imperfect cross-sectional symmetry due to the manufacturing process. The results for the selected design are presented in Table I and visually exemplified in Fig. 4. If more accurate results are needed in terms of natural frequencies, different regions of the stator (i.e., yoke and teeth) must have different values for the anisotropic material properties and the optimization has to be performed on these sets.

III. STATOR VIBRATION RESPONSE USING THE VIBRATION SYNTHESIS METHOD

In the vibration synthesis method, the radial and tangential air-gap force densities F_{rad} and F_{tan} computed using the MST link the electromagnetic and structural domains

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{\text{rad}} &= \frac{1}{2\mu_0} (B_{\text{rad}}^2 - B_{\text{tan}}^2) \\
 F_{\text{tan}} &= \frac{1}{\mu_0} B_{\text{rad}} B_{\text{tan}}
 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where B_{rad} and B_{tan} are the radial and tangential magnetic flux densities, respectively, and μ_0 is the vacuum permeability. The force is expressed as spatially decomposed superposition of the most important excitation shapes using the cosine/sine orthonormal basis according to (6) resulting in time and space amplitude factors $F_{\text{dc}}(t)$, $F_{\text{cos},m}(t)$ and $F_{\text{sin},m}(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{\text{sup}}(t, \mathbf{a}) &= \sum_{m=0}^M F_m(t, \mathbf{a}) \\
 &= F_{\text{dc}}(t) + \sum_{m=1}^M F_{\text{cos},m}(t) \cdot \cos(m\mathbf{a}) + F_{\text{sin},m}(t) \cdot \sin(m\mathbf{a})
 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where F_{sup} is the 2-D superposed air-gap force wave that contains all space-dependent harmonic amplitude factors (F_{dc} and $F_{\text{sin},m}$, $F_{\text{cos},m}$) up to order M .

The vibration is calculated as the superposition of dynamic responses excited by each significant force shape. This is achieved with a modal frequency response solution, having as the excitation $F_{[l],\text{shape}}$ a unitary force shape

$$v_{\parallel e}^i{}_{[l],\text{shape}}(f) = H^i(f) F_{[l],\text{shape}}(f) \quad (7)$$

where $v_{[l],\text{shape}}^i(f)$ is the frequency response in node i for each force-shape excitation, with $H(f)$ the output obtained from modal analysis. The total response in node i $v^i(f)$ is the superposition of all frequency responses scaled with the cosine/sine frequency-domain amplitude factors

$$v^i(f) = \sum_{m=0}^M v_{\parallel \text{DC}}^i(f) F_{\text{DC}}(f) + \sum_{m=1}^M v_{\parallel \text{cos},m}^i F_{\text{cos},m}(f) + v_{\parallel \text{sin},m}^i F_{\text{sin},m}(f) \quad (8)$$

Truncation can be applied to the unitary force shapes based on the machine number of slots and poles. In this case, a 12-slot stator is studied (the method can be applied to any type of stator topologies having a different number of slots), as shown in Fig. 5, and the radial and tangential unitary force-shape responses in the vibration synthesis process are shown in Fig. 6. For the machine under study (presented in Section V-A) if no asymmetries exist (i.e., eccentricity and permanent magnet (PM) demagnetization), it is sufficient to consider only even unitary force shapes. In the present study, additional to the dc components, six pairs of cosine/sine force shapes (from 2 to 12 with a step of 2), both in the radial and tangential directions, are considered. This is done to capture the effects of the most important spatial force harmonics (shown in Fig. 13). It is important to mention that the number

Fig. 5. 3-D FE stator model used in the vibration synthesis method where the unitary force shape $F_{[l],dc}^{rad}$ is shown in red and the output node O where the response is computed is marked with black.

of force shapes used can be extended, leading to an increase in the vibration response accuracy, but at a higher computational cost. Early in the design phase, when only the stator is considered, the additional accuracy improvement can be traded off for computation time decrease because the main goal is to observe the change in trend (i.e., one design iteration relative to another) in vibration response with respect to geometrical parameter modification.

IV. STATOR STRUCTURAL PARAMETRIC MODEL

A. Stator Geometric Parametrization

The stator is parameterized with the same DOFs as in the electromagnetic optimization process [21], shown in Fig. 7, to be used in a multiphysics optimization routine by having a DOF consistency. In this case, TWS represents the tooth width, yt is the yoke thickness, SOAng is the tooth tip angle, TGD is the tooth tip height, SO is the slot opening, Rad_{in} is the stator inner radius, and Rad_{out} is the stator outer radius.

Three DOFs are selected for the data model construction. The main contributor to the stator vibration response is the yoke thickness: a thicker yoke increases the stator stiffness and consequently the modal frequency of the stator. In addition, the tooth thickness, which is important for electromagnetic performance, and the tooth tip angle are selected as the remaining two DOFs. Fig. 8 shows the difference between the minimum and maximum ranges applied in the design process, for each considered variable, while keeping the remaining constant. The slot opening has a big influence on the electromagnetic air-gap forces by affecting the flux density harmonics (the local saturation effect is present) and thus has an influence on the structural vibration response by affecting the source of the vibration. Fig. 8(d) shows that the transmission path (the stator structure) is less affected by the change in the slot opening, but this DOF has to be considered when the full magnetomechanical coupling is used (e.g., in machine

Fig. 6. Unitary force-shape radial displacement responses used in the vibration synthesis process. (a) Radial loads. (b) Tangential loads.

Fig. 7. Stator geometry parameterization where DOFs marked with black are kept fixed and the DOFs marked with red are varied to construct the data-driven model.

optimization routines). As mentioned, in the current study, yt , TWS and SOAng are used as DOFs, but additional DOFs, such as SO, can be added (with additional computational burden) or

Fig. 8. Difference in radial $V_{[I],\cos 4}^i$ for the limit values of DOFs used in the model construction. (a) yt. (b) TWS. (c) SOAng. (d) SO.

replaced with one of the existing DOFs (i.e., replacing SOAng with SO).

B. Unitary Force-Shape Response Transfer Function Estimation

It is assumed that each unitary force-shape response ($V_{[I],\text{shap}}^i(f)$) can be expressed as a system transfer function

$$V_{[I],\text{shap}}^i(s) = \frac{B_{\text{shape},M}(s)}{A_{\text{shape},N}(s)} \quad (9)$$

where $B_{\text{shape}}(s) = b_{\text{shape},M}s^M + b_{\text{shape},(M-1)}s^{(M-1)} + \dots + b_{\text{shape},0}$ is the numerator expressed as a sum of M coefficients [here, M is different from the one in (6)] and $A_{\text{shape}}(s) = a_{\text{shape},N}s^N + a_{\text{shape},(N-1)}s^{(N-1)} + \dots + a_{\text{shape},0}$ is the denominator expressed as a sum of N coefficients. The unitary force-shape responses that are part of the stator vibration model in frequency domain can be estimated as a transfer function in MATLAB using the *tf est* function [22]. For implementation convenience, the number of numerator coefficients (a number of zeros) is set to be equal to the number of denominator coefficients (number of poles): $N = M$. A sensitivity analysis is performed on all 26 force shapes to find the minimum number of zeros and poles that can fully characterize all of the unitary force shapes used in the vibration computation. We can observe from the Bode diagram shown in Fig. 9(a) that $N = 4$ is sufficient to approximate $V_{[I],\cos 2r}^i$, whereas for

$V_{[I],\sin 2r}^i$, $N=12$ is needed to fully approximate the FE-obtained unitary force-shape response. It was observed that $N = 12$ is sufficient for all unitary force-force shapes used in the analysis. A set of unique zeros and poles are obtained using the estimation procedure and overfitting problems do not occur when N is higher than the minimum needed to estimate the FRF, as shown in Fig. 9(a), where the reconstructed unitary force shape for $N = 4$ and $N = 12$ matches the one obtained from FE.

Fig. 9. Bode diagram comparison for a different number of zeros and poles used to estimate the magnitude and phase of two unitary force-shape responses, where the FE results are showed with a black dotted line. (a) Radial $V_{[I],\cos 2}^i$. (b) Radial $V_{[I],\sin 2}^i$.

The value of the unitary force-shape response frequency discretization is correlated with the accuracy (the lower the value, the higher the accuracy) of resonance frequencies and magnitudes used in the zero/poles estimation. In the present study, 10 Hz was found sufficient from an accuracy/computational-time perspective.

In the present work, three DOFs are used to parameterize the stator model, particularly: TWS, yt, and SOAng. By sweeping the DOFs and computing the unitary force-shape responses for each individual stator design, the results can be stored in 4-D LUTs: $V_{[I],\text{shap}}^i(\text{TWS}, \text{yt}, \text{SOAng}, f)$. As shown previously in Section IV-B, a dimensionality reduction can be achieved by approximating the frequency-domain unitary force-shape responses using a transfer functions expressed by an equal number ($N = M = 12$) of zeros and poles according to (9): $V_{[I],\text{shap}}^i(\text{TWS}, \text{yt}, \text{SOAng}, s) = ((B_{\text{shape}}(\text{TWS}, \text{SOAng}, s)) / (A_{\text{shape},12}(\text{TWS}, \text{yt}, \text{SOAng}, s)))$. For each stator structural model, a total number of $26 \cdot 12 = 312$ zeros and poles are saved in LUTs. If more than one output node is needed for vibration computation, a different number of zeros and poles can be selected for the transfer function estimation $N_i M_i$ for that specific node i , while the estimation process remains the same. By adding more output nodes to the vibration computation, the number of zeros and poles stored in the LUT increases exponentially with the number of nodes.

V. VALIDATION OF THE DATA-DRIVEN MODELS

To determine the LUT-based structural model accuracy, three LUT models that use interpolation are constructed based on three different full-factorial sample sizes: 125, 294, and 726 samples and named models FF125, FF294, and F726, as shown in Fig. 10. In Fig. 10, we can observe the parameter loci of three stator FE samples with random generated geometric parameters and one physical machine, further detailed

Fig. 10. Full-factorial samples used in the design exploration of the structural models and parameters loci for the three random generated stators (green) and the IPMSM under test (magenta).

Fig. 11. Different interpolation techniques for the FF726 model applied on $V_{[I],dc}$.

in Section V-A. The first step is to determine the interpolation methods to be used in the LUT models. One can observe in Fig. 11 that the linear interpolation method has the highest accuracy relative to the FE model for most of the unitary force shapes, but this may be particular to the studied case.

The computation time for the unitary force-shape responses (26 force shapes applied to 1428 input nodes and computed on one output node) on a workstation having an Intel Core i7-7920HQ CPU running at 3.10 GHz with 32 GB of RAM for one stator design is approximately 13 min, and it slightly varies with the geometry. Thus, the model generation time for FF125, FF294, and FF726 is approximately 27, 64, and 157 h, respectively. This time can be drastically reduced using parallel processor computing because the response of each unitary force-shape excitation can be computed independently. The computation time for the unitary force-shape response (interpolation and FRF reconstruction) for all LUT models, i.e., FF125, FF294, and FF726, is around 1 s.

A. Analysis of the IPMSM Under Test

The vibration response accuracy of the LUT models is validated using the air-gap force results obtained from the 12-slot/10-pole electric power-steering Internal Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (IPMSM) having a concentrated winding, with the cross section shown in Fig. 12(a) and specifications given in Table II. The electromagnetic FE model is updated using back electromotive force (EMF) test-bench results by changing the PM remanent flux density,

TABLE II
POWER-STEERING IPMSM SPECIFICATIONS

Rated power	800 W
Base speed	1650 RPM
Maximum speed	4000 RPM
Rated current	110 A (rms)
DC-link voltage	12 V
Minimum air-gap	0.5 mm
Stack length	29 mm

Fig. 12. (a) IPMSM cross section and (b) test-updated back EMF.

Fig. 13. Time domain and frequency domain of the air-gap forces. (a) F_{tan} . (b) F_{rad} . (c) F_{rad} . (d) F_{tan} .

with the method presented in [23], with back EMF results shown in Fig. 12(b). The operating point ($i_d = 145.4$ A and $i_q = -36.0$ A) is given by the maximum torque per ampere (MTPA) control strategy, below base speed, on the maximum torque-speed envelope, producing the highest amplitude air-gap forces, thus representing the worst case scenario in terms of NVH attributes.

The radial and tangential force results are shown in Fig. 13 in both time and frequency domains for the proposed MTPA operation point. The run-up vibration response is computed using the vibration synthesis method presented in Section III and the results are shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14. Run-up vibration response spectrogram for the IPMSM under test using the air-gap forces represented in Fig. 13, where the resonance of mode (2, 0) is marked with a dashed-dotted black rectangle and the resonance of mode (3, 0) is marked with a blue dashed rectangle.

TABLE III
UNITARY FORCE-SHAPE AMPLITUDE-PEAK RELATIVE ERROR BETWEEN THE MEAN OF THE THREE RANDOM-GENERATED AND IPMSM UNDER-TEST FE MODELS AND THE PROPOSED DATA-DRIVEN MODELS

	FF125 [%]	FF256 [%]	FF726 [%]
$v_{[I],\cos 2_r}$	0.85	1.7	0
$v_{[I],\cos 4_r}$	18.8	8.54	3.41
$v_{[I],\cos 10_r}$	1.7	1.70	0
$v_{[I],\sin 4_t}$	4.27	0	0.85
$v_{[I],\sin 6_t}$	1.17	0.97	0.58
$v_{[I],\sin 12_t}$	1.17	0.97	0.58

B. Validation of Unitary Force-Shape Responses

The first step in the validation process consists in comparing unitary force shapes obtained from the three LUT-based models and the structural FE models: three randomly generated and the IPMSM under test. These FE models use the same orthotropic material properties obtained in Section II-B for the 3-D stator structural modeling.

The unitary force shapes that have the highest amplitude are also the most impact on the final vibration response. This can be verified by doing a unitary force-shape sensitivity analysis [24]. The first 6 (out of the total 26) are selected for comparison and the results are quantified in Table III, where the arithmetic mean error for the frequency of the four FE models with respect to FF125, FF294, and FF729 is presented. The frequency resolution for the unitary force-shape responses is 10 Hz, with a maximum frequency of 18 kHz.

It can be observed in Fig. 15 that in the case of high-amplitude peaks, models FF294 and FF729 approximate correctly both the amplitude and frequency of the resonance, where FF729 attains the higher accuracy with respect to the FE model. The accuracy decreases with the reduction of samples used in the model generation process (model FF125). In the case of the low-amplitude peaks (the ones that do not significantly contribute to the final vibration response) shown in Fig. 16, the accuracy of the full-factorial models decreases, but still, FF729 has the most accurate representation of the FE model. The results are quantified in Table III.

C. Validation of the Run-Up Vibration Response

The three LUT unitary force-shape models presented in Section V-B (FF125, FF294, and FF729) that include all 26 FRFs presented in Fig. 6 and have the force excitation

Fig. 15. High-displacement amplitude unitary force-shape responses, where the FE results for the IPMSM under test are represented with a magenta line, FF125 with blue diamonds, FF256 with red crosses, and FF726 with black circles. (a) $V_{[I],\cos 2_r}$. (b) $V_{[I],\cos 4_r}$. (c) $V_{[I],\cos 10_r}$. (d) $V_{[I],\sin 4_t}$. (e) $V_{[I],\sin 6_t}$. (f) $V_{[I],\sin 12_t}$.

Fig. 16. Low-displacement amplitude unitary force-shape responses, where the FE results are represented with a magenta line, FF125 with blue diamonds, FF256 with red crosses, and FF726 with black circles. (a) $V_{[I],DC_r}$. (b) $V_{[I],\sin 2_r}$.

presented in Section V-A. The speed step size is 1 r/min. The results are compared with the FE model of the IPMSM under test in terms of vibration displacement for each important order cut that contains a resonance, as shown in Fig. 17. Also, the results are quantified in terms of relative error between the data-driven models and the machine under test for the highest amplitude peak (per mechanical order) together with the speed at which this peak occurs, as shown in Table IV.

Fig. 17. Run-up order cuts, where the FE results are represented with a magenta line, FF125 with blue diamonds, FF256 with red crosses, and FF726 with black circles. (a) $20f_{\text{mech}}$. (b) $30f_{\text{mech}}$. (c) $40f_{\text{mech}}$. (d) $50f_{\text{mech}}$. (e) $60f_{\text{mech}}$. (f) $70f_{\text{mech}}$.

Here, a difference in speed at which the peak occurs is induced by a difference in the unitary force-shape resonance frequency, as shown in Section V-B. The mean error set in terms of amplitude and speed (\bar{A} , $\bar{\omega}$) considering all nine mechanical orders presented is: (2.8, 1.4) for FF125 and (3.1, 2.7) and (0.1, 0) for FF726. From the presented results, we can conclude that a tradeoff between model generation speed and accuracy can be obtained, but it may be the case that a lower sample model (FF125) can be more accurate than a higher sample model (FF256) if the geometry parameters of stator are closer to sample breakpoints used to construct the LUT model.

D. Unitary Force-Shape Responses Computational Cost: Data-Driven Versus FEA

The purpose of building the data-driven model is to decrease the electrical machine vibration computational time at the design stage while maintaining FEA accuracy and having the possibility of fast and accurate system-level analysis. To determine the computational advantage over FEA, a computational efficiency factor for the unitary force-shape responses is introduced k_{ctr} that describes the relative reduction in computation time, similar to the one presented in [14]. By using the unitary

TABLE IV
RUN-UP MECHANICAL ORDERS VIBRATION RESPONSE COMPARISON: RESONANCE PEAK AMPLITUDE (A) AND SPEED (ω) ARITHMETIC MEAN RELATIVE ERROR BETWEEN THE LUT MODELS AND IPMSM UNDER TEST. ORDER 10 IS NOT SHOWN HERE BECAUSE NO RESONANCE OCCURS IN THE SELECTED SPEED RANGE

	FF125		FF256		FF726	
	A[%]	ω [%]	A[%]	ω [%]	A[%]	ω [%]
$20f_{\text{mech}}$	4.58	1.65	0.21	3.30	0.04	0
$30f_{\text{mech}}$	1.35	0.82	2.94	0.82	0.33	0
$40f_{\text{mech}}$	1.25	1.65	1.39	3.3	0.14	0
$50f_{\text{mech}}$	0.07	1.65	1.14	3.3	0.01	0
$60f_{\text{mech}}$	1.59	1.65	5.16	0.82	0	0
$70f_{\text{mech}}$	2.05	1.64	1.55	3.27	0.03	0
$80f_{\text{mech}}$	7.49	1.76	7.23	3.3	0.08	0.11
$90f_{\text{mech}}$	1.41	1.73	0.03	4.08	0.31	0
$100f_{\text{mech}}$	1.24	0.82	2.22	2.45	0.19	0

Fig. 18. Computational feasibility factor where the gray area marks the region where the data-driven models are more time efficient than FEA. (a) 3-DOF models. (b) 4-DOF models.

force-shape approach, the computational time needed to obtain data for one design sample used for building the data-driven models is relatively equivalent to that used for one standard FEA computation (the unitary force-shape computation time is two orders of magnitude higher compared to the zeros/poles identification time, and thus, it is considered negligible), all

things being equal: the same number of unitary force-shape responses, the same number of output nodes, and the same frequency range and frequency steps used in both cases. The unitary force-shape responses computation time does not depend on the number of slots, inner and outer diameter, or stack length, under the assumption that the number of mesh elements for different stator topologies remains the same.

The number of FEA designs used in the machine geometric optimization stage is N_O and the number of designs used to construct the data-driven model N_{LUT} . The computational efficiency factor is the ratio between the two

$$k_{ctr} = \frac{N_{LUT}}{N_O} \quad (10)$$

where the data-driven model is advantageous for a subunitary k_{ctr} . N_{LUT} is given by number of geometric DOFs that are varied during the model construction N_{DOF} and the number of samples (or breakpoints) $N_{samples,k}$ for each k th DOF

$$N_{LUT} = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{DOF}} N_{samples,k} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 18(a) shows the computational feasibility for the three proposed LUT models where, for example, if 2000 designs are considered in the machine geometry optimization stage, the computation time reduction for model FF125, FF256, and FF726 is 93.75%, 87.2%, and 63.7%, respectively. Fig. 18(b) shows the computational feasibility if another DOF is added to the LUT models (i.e., slot opening) with a different number of possible samples (breakpoints) for the newly introduced DOF.

VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This article presents a data-driven structural modeling approach for electrical machine vibration computation. The method is based on constructing zero-pole LUT models that vary in a function of stator geometry. The zeros and poles are obtained by fitting a transfer function to the unitary force shapes obtained from the vibration synthesis method. This means that both the radial and tangential forces that act on the stator teeth can be accounted for in the model. Also, the model can be used both in the optimization process of electrical machines to decrease the computational time and in dynamic system-level simulations.

The main difference between the presented data-driven model and the ones found in the literature is that a test-based material updating process is done before the data are generated and the vibration synthesis method is used for vibration computation thus enabling fast vibroacoustic system-level simulation. The presented data-driven model can capture both in-plane and out-of-plane mode shapes, whereas the model in [13] uses a semianalytical approach where the modal frequencies are obtained from the FEA and the displacement is computed analytically, thus being able to capture only global mode shapes, having less accuracy than a full FEA method, such as the vibration synthesis. The model presented in [14] is similar to the proposed model because it uses FEA for data generation and a zero/pole FRF identification. Salameh *et al.* [14] used the impulse FRF generated by a unit

force for the model construction, while in the present case, the FRFs are unitary force shapes generated by harmonic forces. This implies that to preserve the air-gap force spectrum, attention has to be paid to the number of discretizations per tooth length (as shown in [5]), and the time to generate the data increases with the number of teeth. In the present case, attention has to be paid to the harmonic orders of the unitary force shapes that are related to the machine topology (i.e., number of pole pairs, slots, and winding), and the computational time needed to generate the model does not increase with the number of teeth, but with the number of unitary force shapes applied. Also, the current method is used early in the design cycle, where only the stator is considered for the vibration transmission path, without the presence of housing and additional structural damping elements specifically designed to mitigate NVH issues, whereas Salameh *et al.* [14] considered the full machine assembly.

Guidelines are given for correct transfer function estimation in terms of number of zeros and poles and interpolation method and the model is validated at two different levels. First, four FE samples are compared with the LUT models in terms of unitary force-shape response resonance frequencies. Afterward, the test-correlated electromagnetic model is compared with the LUT models at the vibration response level using a mechanical order analysis. By computing both the relative error for the three different models and the computational cost versus FEA, flexibility is given to the machine designer for selecting the number of designs used to construct the data-driven model. The process was exemplified for one output node, but this can be extended to a multitude of output nodes using the same approach. Also, the model can be extended to the acoustic response by using acoustic pressure transfer functions.

If the stator number of DOFs used in the parametric model has to be increased, the complexity of the LUTs may become too computationally expensive. Thus, different methods can be used to estimate the FRFs, such as deep learning for time series analysis.

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